

MOTIVATION, SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING, SERVICE QUALITY AND SATISFACTION INFLUENCING TO SPECTATOR'S BEHAVIORAL INTENTION IN SICHUAN DIVISION OF CBA LEAGUE

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Abstract

The prosperous development of CBA league cannot be separated from teamwork, individual efforts, enthusiastic fans, strong support from sponsors, publicity from news media and other factors. Along with the rapid development of the tournament, the marketing and management of the CBA league began to fail to keep up with the development of the league itself, and how to develop faster, better, and more sustainably is an important topic currently facing. The study takes the spectator as the entry point, constructs the structural equation model of CBA spectator behavioral intention through quantitative research method, and further analyses the influence of motivation, social media marketing, service quality and satisfaction on CBA spectator behavioral intention. The study was conducted through 857 questionnaire data, which were processed and analysed using SPSS and AMOS software. The results showed that: Spectator motivation has a significant positive impact on the satisfaction of the game. Spectator motivation has a significant positive impact on their behavioral intention to watch games. Spectator motivation has a significant positive impact on their behavioral intention to watch games. Social media marketing has a significant positive impact on CBA spectator satisfaction. Social media marketing has a significant positive impact on CBA spectator's behavioral intention to watch games. Service quality has a significant positive impact on spectator satisfaction. Service quality has a significant positive impact on spectator's behavioral intention. CBA game spectator satisfaction has a significant positive impact on the behavioral intention of watching games. Spectator satisfaction in CBA matches plays a mediating role in the influence between spectator motivation and behavioral intention. CBA game spectator satisfaction plays a mediating role in the influence between social media marketing and behavioral intention. CBA game spectator satisfaction plays an intermediary role in the influence between service quality and behavioral intention.

Keywords: CBA Spectators, Behavioral Intention, Satisfaction, Motivation, Social Media Marketing, Service Quality.

1. INTRODUCTION

So far, CBA league has preliminarily completed the transformation of marketization and professionalism. With the development of China's market, other domestic sports leagues and foreign leagues represented by NBA are rapidly and strongly competing for the Chinese sports market, and CBA league is facing a huge challenge.

From the perspective of the market, China has a huge population base, and the spectator to watch CBA matches is increasing year by year, but the number of live spectators of CBA league still accounts for a minority.

According to the micro evidence survey conducted by scholars (Zhong Huamei, 2020) based on CGSS2015, there were 8,505 samples from 28 provinces/municipalities/autonomous regions in China, among which 7,015 people were never on-site viewers, accounting for 82.48%; 1113 people watched it several times or less a year, accounting for 13.09%; The proportion of monthly, weekly and daily on-site attendance was 2.93%, 1.18% and 0.33%, respectively. It can be shown that the overall market base of Chinese sports events is small, and the number of on-site spectators needs to be increased.

Only by meeting the needs of the spectator to the maximum extent and cultivating the awareness of the spectator to watch the game can we actively promote the positive development of the CBA League. Therefore, from the perspective of the spectator, this paper deeply explores the factors that affect the behavior intentional of the CBA spectator. The main purpose is to increase the number of live spectators of the CBA League, gradually expand the economic share of the sports market, and provide a theoretical basis for the development of China's sports industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Behavioral intention refers to the subjective probability that an individual wants to engage in a certain behavior, reflecting the degree to which an individual is willing to make efforts to carry out a certain behavior. This paper searches relevant literature to find out the factors that affect the behavior intentional of watching games.

Tan Chung et al. (2007), in their study of match-attendance motivation of fans in key football cities, suggested that the study of fans' match-attendance motivation can give root explanations for the occurrence of fans' behaviours, which is a kind of in-depth retrospective causation. The study of motivation can more accurately predict the future behaviour of fans than the study of their past match-attendance behaviour. After analysing the viewing motives for driving behaviour, it facilitates a greater understanding of the behaviour itself, and makes it easier for managers to be able to formulate targeted countermeasures. Chen Zhibin and other scholars (2014) believe that understanding the relationship between fans' motivation to watch matches and their purchasing behaviour is an important basis for professional football clubs to formulate marketing strategies, and Zhang Lei et al. (2017) proposed in the construction and validation of the spectators' motivation model that the spectators' motivation to watch matches has a positive impact on the actual viewing behaviour, and the stronger the spectators' motivation to watch matches is, the more likely they are to watch matches in the future, and the more likely they are to care about sports entertainment and sports consumption. likely to care about sports entertainment and sports consumption.

Funk (2009) points out that different viewing motives reflect people's different viewing needs, and satisfaction increases when these needs are met. In terms of social and escape motives, Song (2014) found that leisure motives have a significant positive impact on people's life and leisure satisfaction through a survey and analysis of leisure sports in China. These motives include the desire to interact with family, friends and others; perceiving the artistic beauty of sports; experiencing the excitement of competition; seeking alternative outcomes; and escaping

from daily routines to relieve stress. Chang (2017), using road running competitions as an example and sampling participants, found that self-actualisation motives, social interaction motives, learning knowledge motives and pressure release motives have a significant positive influence.

Chang Huixin (2016) pointed out that content marketing in social media, which is participatory content created through user involvement, is more likely to attract customers, stimulate communication and encourage users to make purchases and increase web traffic than traditional one-way commercial content. Qian Zhitong et al. (2016) argued that online content marketing can bring together fans of an online community interested in a company's products, which in turn enhances the Internet community economy. He Aizhong et al. (2016) stated in their study that social media marketing has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention.

Zhao Fengmei (2020) used SPORTSEVER and TEAMQUAL tournament service quality perception models, combined with the specificity of basketball, to study the service quality of mass basketball tournaments from the six dimensions of tangibles, responsiveness, reliability (pre-game and in-game), accessibility, safety, and empathy, and put forward hypotheses for the participants' continuous participation behavioral intention, and finally concluded that tournament. Finally, it was concluded that the perceived service quality of the tournament had a significant positive relationship with the basketball hobby level and the intention to participate in the tournament.

Satisfaction plays a very important role in marketing, and consumers who are satisfied with a product will make a commitment to the company, product or service. A large body of literature suggests that consumers who are satisfied with the product offered tend to repurchase. Spears (2004) argues that positive behavioral intentions of spectators can lead to future return to sporting events and spread positive word-of-mouth to potential consumers. Lee (2015) surveyed 224 spectators of a men's professional basketball game in South Korea, and concluded that spectators' satisfaction with the sporting event had a significant impact on team identification and willingness to return. satisfaction had a positive effect on team identification and intention to return. Koo (2014) used a marathon as a study and determined that race participants' satisfaction had a significant positive effect on their behavioral intentions.

Oliver (2010) in *A Behavioral Perspective on the Consumer* refers to the fact that consumer motivation has a direct effect on behavioral intentions, but through the mediating variable satisfaction, the intention to behave is more significant. This shows that the existence of satisfaction's has a mediating role between the two.

Choi et al. (2018) In order to analyse the great difference between virtual golf and traditional golf, to better promote virtual golf, as well as to play the value of virtual golf. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to investigate 209 virtual golf participants, and the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and behavioral intention was analysed, and it was concluded that there is a mediating role of customer satisfaction in service quality over behavioral intention.

Li Song (2017) selected live spectators of three of the six brand events to conduct a survey, obtained a total of 518 valid samples through random sampling, and then used structural equation modeling to validate the constructed relationship model between perceived event service quality, spectator satisfaction, and behavioral intention to watch the tournament. The results show that satisfaction plays an intermediary role in the process of perceived event service quality influencing spectators' intention to watch the event, in which 39.265% of the influence of perceived event service quality on spectators' intention to watch the event is achieved through satisfaction.

In summary, the main factors influencing behavioral intention include motivation, social media marketing, service quality, and satisfaction. And satisfaction also has a mediating role in many literatures. These literatures provide a theoretical basis for the research hypothesis of this paper.

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Based on the research of other scholars, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

- Hypothesis 1:** Spectator motivation has a significant positive impact on the satisfaction of the game.
- Hypothesis 2:** Spectator motivation has a significant positive impact on their behavioral intention to watch games.
- Hypothesis 3:** Social media marketing has a significant positive impact on CBA spectator satisfaction.
- Hypothesis 4:** Social media marketing has a significant positive impact on CBA spectator's behavioral intention to watch games.
- Hypothesis 5:** Service quality has a significant positive impact on spectator satisfaction.
- Hypothesis 6:** Service quality has a significant positive impact on spectator's behavioral intention.
- Hypothesis 7:** CBA game spectator satisfaction has a significant positive impact on the behavioral intention of watching games.
- Hypothesis 8:** Spectator satisfaction in CBA matches plays a mediating role in the influence between spectator motivation and behavioral intention.
- Hypothesis 9:** CBA game spectator satisfaction plays a mediating role in the influence between social media marketing and behavioral intention.
- Hypothesis 10:** CBA game spectator satisfaction plays an intermediary role in the influence between service quality and behavioral intention.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to the above literature, CBA spectators' behavioral intention is affected by many factors, including spectator motivation, social media marketing, event service quality and satisfaction. According to the hypothesis proposed by various scholars, The author made the "cba spectator behavioral intention questionnaire", after many times on-site distribution of questionnaires, a total of 900 copies, recovered 857 valid questionnaires. The author used SPSS and AMOS software to organize and analyze the questionnaire data, and constructed the structural equation model of motivation, social media marketing, service quality, satisfaction, and behavioral intention respectively, and finally constructed the structural equation model of motivation, social media marketing, service quality, satisfaction, and behavioral intention after the validation factor analysis to check the credibility and validity of the structural equation model.

5. STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELLING

Combined with the hypotheses of the previous research, structural equation modelling was constructed and the correlation lines between the independent variables were drawn, and substituting the data into AMOS 26 yielded the following results.

Figure 1: Structural equation model

The non-standard model estimation residuals can be viewed through AMOS to be all positive, with no illegal estimation, and then switched to standardised estimation to produce the results in Figure above. From the above figure, it can be seen that the ratio of chi-square to degrees of freedom is 1.073 less than 3, the indicator is qualified. gfi value is 0.943 greater than 0.9, the indicator is qualified. agfi value is 0.937 greater than 0.9, the indicator is qualified. rmsea value is 0.009 less than 0.08, the indicator is qualified. nfi value is 0.948 greater than 0.9, the indicator is qualified, ifi value is 0.996 is greater than 0.9, the indicator is qualified. Combined, the above indicators show that the structural equation model is well adapted.

Table 1: Path coefficients between variables

Variable	Std.	Unstd.	S.E.	C.R.	P
SA <--- MO	0.195	0.202	0.063	3.212	0.001
SA <--- SM	0.334	0.385	0.072	5.304	***
SA <--- SQ	0.192	0.226	0.075	3.028	0.002
BI <--- MO	0.284	0.233	0.048	4.82	***
BI <--- SM	0.156	0.143	0.054	2.628	0.009
BI <--- SQ	0.22	0.205	0.056	3.639	***
BI <--- SA	0.187	0.148	0.049	3.025	0.002

Note: ***<0.001

From the table above, it can be seen that in the path analysis of motivation, social media marketing, and service quality on satisfaction as well as behavioural intention, the p-value is less than 0.05 and the standard path coefficients are all positive, indicating that there is a significant positive effect of each path.

6. MEDIATED EFFECTS TEST

The Bootstrapping mediation effects test of Preacher and Hayes (2008) was used (set to 5000 iterations, the method provides a 95% confidence interval estimate of the mediation effect, which means that the mediation effect is not significant if the interval estimate contains 0, and significant if the interval estimate does not contain 0. The test was run through Amos to obtain the following results. The following results were obtained from the Amos runs.

Table 2: Mediation effect test

Variable	Estimate	S.E.	Z	Bias-Corrected 95% CI		Two Tailed Significance
				Lower	Upper	
MO→SA→BI	0.030	0.014	2.143	0.009	0.068	0.002
SM→SA→BI	0.057	0.024	2.375	0.019	0.117	0.002
SQ→SA→BI	0.034	0.017	2.000	0.009	0.078	0.004

Note: Estimating of 5,000 bootstrap sample.

As can be seen from the table, the Bias-Corrected 95% CI for motivation to satisfaction to behavioral intention has an interval of 0.009 to 0.068, and the interval estimate does not contain 0, indicating that satisfaction mediates significantly between motivation and behavioral intention. The interval of the Bias-Corrected 95% CI for social media marketing to satisfaction

to behavioral intention was 0.019 to 0.117, and the interval estimate did not contain 0, indicating a significant mediating effect of satisfaction between social media marketing and behavioral intention. The interval of the Bias-Corrected 95% CI for service quality to satisfaction to behavioral intention was 0.009 to 0.078, and the interval estimate did not contain 0, indicating a significant mediating effect of satisfaction between service quality and behavioral intention.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper takes the spectator in Sichuan Division of CBA League as the survey object to study the influence of spectator motivation, social media marketing, service quality and satisfaction on behavioral intention. On the basis of literature demonstration on the motivation of watching matches, social media marketing, service quality, satisfaction and behavior intention, 857 valid questionnaire data were investigated and collected by quantitative research method. The confirmatory factor analysis of the collected data was carried out by SPSS and AMOS, and a structural equation model was constructed. Find the important factors that affect the spectator's behavior intention. Finally, the following conclusions are drawn:

Spectator motivation has a significant positive impact on the satisfaction of the game. Spectator motivation has a significant positive impact on their behavioral intention to watch games. Spectator motivation has a significant positive impact on their behavioral intention to watch games. Social media marketing has a significant positive impact on CBA spectator satisfaction. Social media marketing has a significant positive impact on CBA spectator's behavioral intention to watch games. Service quality has a significant positive impact on spectator satisfaction. Service quality has a significant positive impact on spectator's behavioral intention. CBA game spectator satisfaction has a significant positive impact on the behavioral intention of watching games. Spectator satisfaction in CBA matches plays a mediating role in the influence between spectator motivation and behavioral intention. CBA game spectator satisfaction plays a mediating role in the influence between social media marketing and behavioral intention. CBA game spectator satisfaction plays an intermediary role in the influence between service quality and behavioral intention.

8. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The CBA league is spread across 20 cities in China, and there are big differences in the level of economic development, personnel structure and venue facilities between cities. In this study, only the CBA spectators in Sichuan, which is located in the western part of China, with special geographic environment and cultural qualities, were selected for the study. The results of this paper do not represent the overall situation of CBA spectators in the whole country. Therefore, the study has some limitations in the selection of regions. This study is the author's first study of the factors influencing the spectator's CBA spectator viewing behavioral intentions, and a more comprehensive and in-depth survey and research will be carried out after the study has formed preliminary research results. In order to select a more comprehensive survey sample, the CBA spectators in various regions of China will be surveyed at a later stage to enrich the

composition of the sample, which is conducive to understanding the basic situation of the overall spectator.

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